

MINIMALISM AND ITS MAIN FEATURES IN ART AND LITERATURE

Sirazeeva Karina Rishatovna

Student of UzSWLU Master Department Tashkent, Uzbekistan

mail: karri199825@gmail.com

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Minimalism shows simplicity in style or technique and can be used as art, music, architecture, design forms. Everything starts with the choice of daily clothes and with the usage of kitchen utensils in routine life. Like Peter Crook said in his explanation “What is minimalism?”: *“Minimalism is removing excess and distractions to create space for what’s truly important.”*¹ For instance, having too much choices in the shop shelves make people to confuse whether this product is better than the other one. That’s why human beings are able to focus on what truly is important only when they see a smaller number of products in front of them.

Minimalism in Art is a tendency that deals with the primary elements of an artwork. It removes needless elements and emphasizes the space around the main object. This trend began in the early 60s (after WWII) in New York as a protest against Abstract Expressionism. Examples of Minimalism art are paintings, minimalist sculpture, and interior design. Cinzia Franceschini, who is an expert in Italian History of Art Criticism, claimed: *“In Minimalism, the forms of expressiveness, emotionality, identity are suppressed in order to emphasize the objectivity and the essence of the artwork”*².

The main feature of Minimalistic Art was to be against expressive and abstract nature, maybe it seems somehow rebellious because it shares with the simplicity of the meaning, color, and form. Another characteristic is the usage of colors. The painters tried to implement neutral colors to show the work as it is without personal expression. And of course, they added geometric shapes, such as squares, circles, and triangles. These shapes are not usually aesthetically pleasing or do not have senses. Cedric VanEeno in his article stated: *“Make it pure and simple”* – this brief sentence could have served as the motto for Minimalism, an art movement that really began in the 1960s, although there were some earlier manifestations³.

Moreover, not only just paintings are famous for Minimalistic tendencies, but Music, Cinematography, and Fashion. For example, the term “minimal music” was coined by Michael Nyman in 1970. Danish composer Henning Christiansen

¹ [What is Minimalism? | Minimalism for Beginners \(youtube.com\)](#)

² Cinzia Franceschini. Minimalism Art Movement- Rome,2018

³ Cedric VanEeno. Minimalism in Art and Design: Concept, influences, implications and perspectives. Journal of Fine and Studio Art Vol. 2(1), June 2011- pp.7-12

first used Minimalism in his 10-minute work. In addition, different filmmakers create their movies in a Minimalistic way, such as Robert Bresson, Chantal Akerman, Carl Theodor Dreyer, and Yasujirō Ozu. They try to show their works as it is with the usage of a simple camera, but there should be minimal use of score. Thus, Minimalism as a trend is also in Fashion Industry. It first appeared in 1970 and the creator of this concept was Susie Faux. The main feature of this tendency was to have clothes with two or three colors, which can be combined with casual style.

Minimalism as a literary tendency is a style of writing, which focuses on specific features and expresses descriptive language or a backstory. This trend aim is to write about the ordinary life of people through simple sentences. There are no detailed descriptions of the characters' thoughts; readers should interpret them himself/herself. Minimalism in literature appeared in 1960 in America; it means that Minimalism in art influenced a lot on the literary world. On the one hand, people consider Ezra Pound and William Carlos Williams to be the founders of the literary trend. On the other hand, they believed that Ernest Hemingway and Samuel Beckett were contributors to American Minimalism. Minimalism was popular from the 1980s till the present day. The representatives of contemporary writers are Cormac McCarthy, Brett Easton Ellis, and, of course, George Saunders.

There are three main characteristics of Minimalism in literature:

1. The less you write, the better it will be

It means that in Minimalism descriptions should be short and simple. Moreover, the quantity of verbs is more than the number of adjectives. As there is no need for describing details, so adjectives are also unimportant parts of speech.

Madison Smartt Bell wrote in his essay "Less is Less" *"a trim, minimal style, an obsessive concern for surface detail, a tendency to ignore or eliminate distinctions among people it renders, and a studiedly deterministic, at times nihilistic, vision of the world."*⁴

2. The simpler sentence, the deeper meaning

When the reader faces a short and simple sentence, the first thing that comes to his/her mind is that everything should be easy to understand. The main aim of Minimalism was to write about the facts.

3. Uncomplicated plot

⁴Madison Smartt Bell. Essay: Less is Less- The USA: Harper's Magazine,1986 p.65

The plots are linear and it is easy to observe them in Minimalism. The purpose is to reflect the simple life of characters and show their attitude toward different situations, where they can be. It is better to see either self-development or degradation of the personages.

The best examples of writers in Minimalism can be Tobias Wolff with his collection of short stories "Hunter in the Snow"⁵ or the story "Next Door"⁶, or Richard Ford and his "Rock Springs"⁷ or story- "Going to the Dogs"⁸, and Ernest Hemingway- "In our time"⁹ or story- "Chapter VI"¹⁰. Furthermore, there is George Saunders and his great collection of short stories. For instance, "Tenth of December: stories"¹¹ is one of the best-known collections among his works.

Minimalism in Uzbek literature, as in other contexts, focuses on concise language, simple narrative structures, and a tendency to imply rather than overtly explain. This style can serve to foreground the essence of human experiences and emotions against the backdrop of Uzbek culture, history, and societal norms. By stripping down to the basics, Uzbek writers can offer powerful, nuanced insights into their subjects, encouraging readers to engage actively with the text to uncover deeper meanings. Minimalism isn't a widely recognized movement in Uzbek literature, which has a rich tradition with roots in classical Persian and Turkic literary cultures. However, contemporary Uzbek writers who are known for a more concise, pared-down style, echoing the minimalist aesthetic, may include:

- Abdulla Qodiriy and his collections of short stories: "From Mahzum the Simpleton's Diary"¹², "What Does Irritate Toshpo'lat Say?"¹³. While he is not a minimalist in the strict sense, his works often focus on clear, strong narratives;
- Hamid Ismailov: Though his style can be elaborate, he employs a certain economy of language that could be considered minimalist in some of his works.

⁵ Tobias Wolff. *Hunters in the Snow: A Collection of Short Stories*- The USA: Vintage/Ebury A Division of Random House, July 1982

⁶ Tobias Wolff. *Hunters in the Snow: A Collection of Short Stories*- The USA: Vintage/Ebury A Division of Random House, July 1982- p.3

⁷ Richard Ford. *Rock Springs* (short story collection)- The USA: Atlantic Monthly Press, 1987

⁸ Richard Ford. *Rock Springs* (short story collection)- The USA: Atlantic Monthly Press, 1987-p.3

⁹ Ernest Hemingway. *In Our Time* (short story collection)- The USA: Boni & Liveright, 1986

¹⁰ Ernest Hemingway. *In Our Time* (short story collection)- The USA: Boni & Liveright, 1986-p.13

¹¹ George Saunders. *Tenth of December: A Collection of Short Stories*- The USA: Random House Trade Paperbacks, 2014

¹² Abdulla Qodiriy. *From Mahzum the Simpleton's Diary* - Uzbekistan: Abdulla Qodiriy nomidagi xalq merosi nashriyoti, 2011

¹³ Abdulla Qodiriy. *What Does Irritate Toshpo'lat Say*- Uzbekistan: Abdulla Qodiriy nomidagi xalq merosi nashriyoti, 1926

It's important to note that Uzbek literature, both classical and modern, often features rich descriptive language and a strong emphasis on cultural and historical themes, which might not align with minimalist principles. Uzbek writers who embrace minimalism might not be well-known internationally, and their work might be categorized differently within the context of Uzbek literary discourse.

Minimalism can be in different forms and shapes and those 3 main features above are only general information of how to distinguish minimalistic form of the work among the whole literary tendencies. However, the reader finds not only those concepts during analyzing works. Firstly, there is minimalism in style: cutdown vocabulary, stripped-down syntax, where there are no complex sentences and, of course, unemotional tone of the work. Secondly, it is a minimalism of the material: few personages, minimal exposition, minimal scenes, minimal plot (*"all that David Copperfield kind of crap¹⁴," says J.D. Salinger's Catcher in The Rye*).

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¹⁴ Jerome David Salinger. Catcher in The Rye- The USA: Little/Brown and Company, 1951, p.2

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